

BUILDING BABEL IN ROME: ZAHA HADID'S MAXXI

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Abstract

This paper begins by framing Zaha Hadid's MAXXI—Italy's national museum of 21st-century arts—as both an expression of the ideals and models that informed Rome's urban renovation at the turn of the millennium and a somewhat contradictory example of the simultaneous proliferation of cultural institutions across Europe—what French art historian Jean Clair called “a grey mantle of museums,” echoing Raul Glaber's metaphor of a white mantle of churches spreading over medieval Europe.

Built on the site of early-20th-century military barracks, Hadid's design retained only two of the existing buildings, preserving their masonry shells, plaster facades, tiled roofs, and cast-iron frames. The lobby and main galleries unfold within a new cluster of curved, longitudinal volumes that trace the western edge of the plot, with exhibition spaces stacked and grafted at varying heights and angles.

From the outside, one can only guess at building's shape and internal layout. This “opacity” is not resolved upon entry—if anything, the sense of disorientation is intensified. Hadid herself described MAXXI as an “overchanging event in space”: a work of architecture not meant to be grasped at once but gradually revealed through exploration.

Only one reference was explicitly cited by the architect for this project: Frank Lloyd Wright's Guggenheim in New York (1959). In Hadid's view, the visitor's journey of MAXXI—funneled along longitudinal galleries arranged in a quasi-ascensional sequence—mirrored, in reverse, the spatial logic of Wright's descending ramp. Both designs were structured around movement: a spiraling path in New York and a fragmented progression in Rome. Both rejected the supposed neutrality of the “white cube” in favor of a highly connotated exhibition space. And both served the needs of artists and curators while simultaneously challenging them to adapt and respond to architecture.

1. Introduction

More than twenty-five years have passed since the launch of the competition for MAXXI—Italy’s national museum of contemporary art in Rome—fifteen since its opening, and nine since the death of its architect, the Iraqi-born, London-based Zaha Hadid (1950–2016). These figures are not just historical footnotes. They suggest that the time has come to look at this project—and the decisions that shaped it—with a measure of distance, removed from the enthusiasms and controversies it once elicited (**Fig. 1**). And, perhaps more tellingly, they indicate that a building once—and at times still—pitched as a promise of the future has, somewhat inevitably, become an object of history.

MAXXI was conceived with an explicit ambition in mind: to update Rome’s and Italy’s standing in the international art world;¹ and with an implicit one: to mark a cultural shift, announcing the country’s belated entry into the circuits of global architectural production—in the words of Paolo Portoghesi, to “stir the muddy waters of Italian architecture.”²

Figure 1. Zaha Hadid Architects, MAXXI, Rome, Italy, 1998–2009. Enthusiasm and controversy surrounding the museum’s inauguration: Cover page of an article in a lighting design publication (detail). Source: Barr, “Roman Conqueror,” 32.

If one were searching for precedents, one need to look no further than Bilbao. The success of Frank Gehry's Guggenheim (1991-97) as a catalyst for economic growth and urban rebranding served as a direct template for MAXXI³ and, more broadly, for regeneration processes across Europe, cementing the cliché that "the museum was the panacea to every city's ills"⁴—one embraced by administrators, planners, commentators, and laymen alike. This conviction—or rather, this "belief"—contributed to what art historian Jean Clair provocatively described as a "grey mantle" of museums spreading over Europe at the turn of the millennium, echoing Raoul Glaber's image of a white mantle of churches in medieval times.⁵

Bilbao also made clear that not just any museum would do: successful regeneration and rebranding demanded a building with strong image capital—they required an "icon." And it was precisely such an icon—one that could stand apart from the countless others already embedded in Rome's secular and religious past—that administrators and politicians were chasing with MAXXI.

The site chosen for the new museum, however, was rather unassuming: not a prominent bend on the riverfront—as in Bilbao—but an awkward L-shaped plot just outside Rome's historic center, in the Flaminio District, one of the urban expansions sketched in the city's first modern masterplan of 1909 (**Fig. 2**). The plot was dense with low, pitch-roofed industrial buildings from the early twentieth century, repurposed as military barracks since World War I. To the east, it bordered the nave of the Basilica of S. Croce in Via Flaminia (1912-13) and the blank backs of six- to seven-story residential blocks. To the west, other former barracks housed a police station. To the north and south, the plot opened onto two broad streets: Via Masaccio and Via Guido Reni (**Fig. 3**).

Figure 2. Urban plan of central Rome, Italy, showing the Flaminio District and the MAXXI site highlighted in red. Drawing by the author.

Figure 3. Aerial view of the MAXXI competition site (*Caserma Montello*), c. 1985. Elaboration by the author on an aerial image from Google Earth.

Long before MAXXI, the district already carried a distinct modern imprint, shaped by a sequence of remarkable works built from the late 1950s onward: Pierluigi Nervi's *Flaminio Stadium* (with A. Nervi, 1957-59), *Corso di Francia* viaduct (1960), and *Palazzetto dello Sport* (with A. Vitellozzi, 1956-57); the pilotis-raised residential blocks of the Olympic Village by Cafiero, Libera, Luccichenti, Monaco, and Moretti (1958-59); as well as the later S. Valentino parish complex by Francesco Berarducci (1979-87), and Renzo Piano's performing arts center, or *Parco della Musica* (1994-2002).

The competition attracted proposals from well-known international and Italian practitioners.⁶ The appeal was clear: designing a major public building in Rome was a rare opportunity, especially since hardly any had been built in the previous three decades. From an initial shortlist of fifteen teams, four finalists were chosen: Eduardo Soto de Moura, Rem Koolhaas (OMA), Steven Holl, and Zaha Hadid. The winner was ultimately decided by a single vote, with Holl narrowly missing out⁷ (**Fig.4**).

Figure 4. Steven Holl Architects, competition model for a contemporary arts center in Rome (MAXXI), 1998. Photograph by Sebastiano Luciano. Source: “The National center for Contemporary Art and Architecture.”

Selecting Hadid—an architect well known for her unwillingness to compromise—yielded, unsurprisingly, an “all-or-nothing building:” one that broke sharply with context and convention. For Hadid, too, MAXXI marked a break. Formally, the project sits right at the transition between the “jagged” and “flinty” lines of her early work, such as the Vitra Fire Station (1991-93), and the “oozy and honeyed” forms of her later buildings—what Thomas de Monchaux summarized as the shift from “zigzags” to “wiggles;” “lines” to “curves;” “scores” to “squishes;” “breaks” to “ripples;” “hardness” to “softness.”⁸ The more significant transition, however, is one less apparent to the eye. As Nerma Cridge has noted, MAXXI, one of Hadid’s most celebrated works, is also the last that can be clearly tied to her own hand, before the sheer volume, scale, and global spread of commissions—and the office’s evolving workflows and representational routines—steered the practice away from the highly personal line of inquiry she first developed at the AA in the late 1970s.⁹

2. A QUASI-URBAN FABRIC

To understand Hadid’s design, it is useful to recall the conditions set out in the competition brief. MAXXI was never meant to be an enclosed, self-contained object, but an *art campus*, following models such as the Menil Collection in Houston (1987) and Vienna’s MUMOK (2001).¹⁰ The brief even imagined art installations spilling into the surrounding neighborhood—an ambition later deemed unfeasible and dropped. It also required that part of the existing barracks be retained and adapted, and it articulated expectations for the architectural language of the new museum. In particular, it warned against “the nonchalant use of certain architectural gimmicks, which all too often ends up in equally superficial ‘neo’ and ‘post’ proposals”¹¹—a point underscored by naming Mario Botta’s MART in Rovereto (1988-2002) and James Stirling’s *Neue Staatsgalerie* in Stuttgart (1979-84) as cautionary counterexamples. Above all, the brief demanded exhibition halls that were not neutral containers—not “white cubes”—but spaces capable of engaging and challenging curators and artists (**Fig. 5**).

Figure 5. Zaha Hadid Architects, MAXXI, Rome, Italy, 1998–2009. Competition model. Photo: Sebastiano Luciano. Source: The National center for Contemporary Art and Architecture.”

However radical it may appear, Hadid’s scheme met these requirements with almost pedantic accuracy. It did retain two of the low, double-pitched industrial buildings, preserving their masonry shells, plaster facades, tiled roofs, and cast-iron frames: one aligned to Via Guido Reni, the main access road to the south; the other set along the plot’s eastern edge. It did yield a quasi-urban fabric of volumes—part straight, part curved (the pencil-and-compass kind, not the spline way)—clustered along the western boundary and skillfully negotiating the constraints of the L-shaped plot. And it did result in exhibition spaces that were anything but neutral: longitudinal galleries stacked and grafted at varying heights and angles.

The museum’s layout draws on a dense mesh of geometric construction lines that connect the plot with roads, edges, and corner points of the surrounding twentieth-century urban grid (**Fig. 6**). Some of these alignments are plainly legible on site, such as the orientation of an adjacent street; others feel more forced, as if splinters of the

city had been projected onto the plot through abstract conceptual operations. The construction of the plan recalls formal strategies deployed in Hadid's earlier works—Vitra (1991-93) (**Fig. 7**), the Spittelau viaduct (1994), the Carnuntum Museum (1993), and the IIT Campus (1998)—each anchored in extended fields of oblique vectors that reach outwards into the urban fabric. In this approach to planimetric composition, one might also sense a distant response—at once a nod and a rebuttal—to the axial rigor of what Alvin Boyarsky called the “dogmatic late-nineteenth-century urbanism” championed by Hadid's former teacher in London, Leon Krier.¹²

Figure 6. Zaha Hadid Architects, MAXXI, Rome, Italy, 1998–2009. Planimetric sketches and geometric construction lines. Source: Hadid, *Zaha Hadid: 1996–2001*, 178.

Figure 7. Zaha Hadid Architects, Vitra Fire Station, Weil am Rhein, 1991–93. Site plan and geometric construction lines. Source: Hadid, *Zaha Hadid: 1992–1995*, 42.

The original competition entry included two additional buildings, intended to occupy part of what is now the entrance court, between the galleries to the west and the preserved barrack to the east. These volumes—the missing threads in the project’s geometric fabric—were never built due to budget constraints and construction delays, leaving MAXXI, in Hadid’s own words, as “an unfinished work”¹³ (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Zaha Hadid Architects, MAXXI, Rome, Italy, 1998–2009. Bird’s-eye view rendering and photograph. Source: Baldwin, “Render to Reality: Zaha Hadid Architects Bring Futuristic Visions to Life.”

The new volumes hinge on one dominant tectonic element: the wall. Hadid went so far as to describe MAXXI as a “linear, layered series of walls” that “irrigate the site”, structuring interior and exterior spaces alike.¹⁴ These walls shift in plan and section—sometimes straight, sometimes slanted; sometimes grounded, sometimes lifted into beams or cantilevers to frame passages, gaps, and transitions. This strategy, too, was not new at MAXXI, but built on experiments such as the Landesgartenschau in Weil am Rhein (1997), the extension of the Reina Sofia Museum (1999), and temporary installations like *Wish Machine* (Vienna, 1996) and *Paper Art* (Düren, 1996).

Unlike the bricks and ashlar of Roman masonry, MAXXI’s walls are neither assembled nor dressed in discrete units but cast in concrete—fair-faced on the outside and plastered on the inside. Hadid called this material choice “puritanical”—a reflection of modernist ideals of tectonic honesty.¹⁵ Her concrete surfaces, however, were not aiming for material clarity or expressiveness but for near-abstract uniformity. That goal was only partly achieved—much to the architect’s frustration—ultimately producing what Portoghesi, an early critic of the building, wryly but not inaccurately described as a “slick” and “oily” texture.¹⁶

The walls—hollowed to contain the building’s service shafts—gain even more prominence because MAXXI has no conventional roof. Instead, glazed infills span the tops of the walls, divided by bundles of longitudinal beams that act as monumental louvers—their profiles echoing and reinforcing the orientations of the walls. The beams themselves are steel profiles clad in fiber-reinforced concrete—a choice that carries, by all means, a far less “puritanical” connotation.

3. PROMENADES

Hadid cited only one reference for the design of MAXXI: Frank Lloyd Wright's Guggenheim Museum in New York (1943-59). In her view, the visitor's journey at MAXXI—funneled through longitudinal galleries arranged in a quasi-ascensional sequence—mirrored, in reverse, the spatial logic of Wright's ramp.¹⁷

Before unpacking the implications—and contradictions—of this analogy, it is worth recalling that Hadid's engagement with the Guggenheim had been anything but superficial. Her first major exhibition project took place in Wright's rotunda, when she was invited to design the show *The Great Utopia: The Russian and Soviet Avant-Garde* (1992). Her proposal hinged on two exhibition devices. In the central void, she envisioned a large-scale interpretive reconstruction of Tatlin's *Monument to the Third International* (1919-20). This idea, compelling but ultimately unfeasible, remained on paper. Along the ramp, she introduced a sequence of thin, fin-like red panels that broke the steady flow of the spiral into a syncopated rhythm (**Fig. 9**). Decades later, for her own retrospective at the Guggenheim (2006) she would again add a rhythmic counterpoint to the ramp through another off-axis sequence of exhibition supports.

Figure 9. Zaha Hadid Architects, *The Great Utopia: The Russian and Soviet Avant-Garde, 1915–1932*, Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum, New York, U.S., 1992–93. Installation view, Zig Zag Wall, rotunda level 2. Photo: David Heald. © The Solomon R. Guggenheim Foundation.

Turning vertical circulation into a substantive component of the exhibition path was something that Hadid explored consistently in her museums, both before and after MAXXI. A notable example is the CAC in Cincinnati (1997-2003). There she positioned staircases at shifting points across the plan, compelling visitors to cross through the building to reach the galleries above. A similar strategy appears in MAXXI, where staircases—volumetric shafts clad in the same black, opaque metal sheets that she used in Cincinnati—cut through the lobby and unfolded at the intersection of different galleries. Their sculptural profiles and meandering outlines act as both a “form of movement”—an invitation to walk—and a spectacle of the “movement of form,”¹⁸ suggesting, as Lewis Mumford once wrote of Wright's rotunda, that “the whole building is in motion, and the spectator must be in motion, too.”¹⁹

Hadid's analogy between MAXXI and the Guggenheim extends beyond their staging of vertical circulation. The broader point is that, in both cases, the exhibition space itself becomes a site of movement (**Fig. 10**). This idea

is neither new nor exclusive to Wright and Hadid. Nineteenth-century museums relied for the most part on continuous corridors and enfilades, and many modern experiments into the typology of the exhibition likewise conflated path and display. One might think of Le Corbusier's *spirals*—from the unbuilt *Mundaneum* in Geneva (1929) and Contemporary Art Museum in Paris (1931), to their built counterparts in Ahmedabad (1951-57), Chandigarh (1952-56), and Tokyo (1954-55)—all the way back to the first instance of his *promenade architecturale* at the Villa La Roche (1923-25), at once a domestic space and a private gallery for Purist painting.²⁰ These precedents suggest that a corridor becomes a *promenade*—and an exhibition space becomes a site of movement—not through movement alone, but through the *quality* of that movement: how the spaces are staged, how they are crossed, and how the sequence unfolds over time.

Figure 10. Zaha Hadid Architects, MAXXI, Rome, Italy, 1998–2009. First and second floor plans. Source: “MAXXI Museum / Zaha Hadid Architects.”

It is precisely this *quality* that Hadid invoked when she describes movement in MAXXI as drifting.²¹ This term is telling. It proposes a less directed mode of motion than *promenade* does. Drifting is unbounded; a promenade is structured and purposeful. The latter relies on orientation and on tropes such as anticipation, build-up, release. Drifting suggests the opposite: the impossibility of full orientation, the likelihood of surprise, the expectation that getting lost or doubling back is part of the experience. And one does, indeed, get lost at MAXXI. The longitudinal galleries—sometimes flat, sometimes stepped, sometimes slanted—intersect at unexpected junctions, beginning and ending, as Desley Luscombe observed, “without hierarchy and with no clear order.” Even after hours of wandering—after considerable “physical and physiological effort”—it is difficult to picture the building as a totality.²²

Internal partitions reinforce this effect. MAXXI's five galleries unfold through overlapping linear volumes, yet they must also function autonomously to accommodate parallel exhibitions. As a result, their volumes are subdivided by glass diaphragms, infill walls, or service cores. In early renderings these elements are conspicuously absent: only the longitudinal walls and decks appear, with gallery spaces stretching without interruption²³ (Fig. 11). The competition documents do mention "potential partitions hanging from the ceilings,"²⁴ movable and endlessly reconfigurable, but this hyper-flexible solution proved incompatible with the operational realities of the museum and was abandoned.

Figure 11. Zaha Hadid Architects, MAXXI, Rome, Italy, 1998–2009. Renderings from the competition and conceptual design phase, c. 1998–2001. Source: Hadid, *Relazione al progetto definitivo* (2001/11 – 2002/06), 21–25.

As in a labyrinth, where proximity to the center or edge can be inferred by glimpsing what lies beyond the walls, visitors at MAXXI get a cue of orientation from their vertical position within the building. The higher one is, the closer to the end of the journey. One should remember that—while the exhibition paths of Wright's rotunda and Le Corbusier's *Mundaneum* descended from top to bottom—MAXXI is structured as an ascent, a climb upward. Its route stops at a small gallery, cut short by a glazed wall serving as belvedere. After that, visitors are through and must retrace their steps—back through the galleries or down toward the lobby (Fig. 12).

More puzzling than this abrupt ending, is the orientation of the belvedere itself. The glazed wall does not look toward the nearby bend of the Tiber and Monte Mario hill—also the site of Raffaello's *Villa Madama* (1518–25)—which might have built a visual connection between city and landscape, or present and past. Nor does it frame the preserved military barracks down below, or the works of modern architecture nearby—establishing ideal lineages. It does not even look onto the museum's own volumes—which might have offered a sense of closure, as if viewing (and finally understanding) a labyrinth from above. Instead, it opens—at a slightly oblique angle—onto the façades and blank party walls of neighboring residential blocks.

Figure 12. Zaha Hadid Architects, MAXXI, Rome, Italy, 1998–2009. The truncated end of Gallery 5, 2009. Photo: © Giulia Carboni. Source: Besomi, “Inauguran el MAXXI, Roma / Zaha Hadid.”

This choice is so odd, and yet so consistent in the evolution of the project that it is hard not to read it as intentional. It is all the more striking when compared, for example, with Steven Holl’s close-second scheme—which also featured a raised longitudinal gallery but oriented it, more straightforwardly, toward the river.

There is no evidence of why Hadid opted for this solution, and all we are left with is speculation. One might attempt an open-ended reading—one that invites doubt rather than certainty—by drawing another, more imaginative parallel between Wright’s Guggenheim and Hadid’s MAXXI. Shortly after the Guggenheim’s completion, Lewis Mumford noted the now-familiar parallel between the rotunda and an inverted ziggurat, tapered toward the base.²⁵ Yet it was Wright himself who first called his museum an “optimistic ziggurat,” in a drawing and letter to Hilla Rebay from 1944.²⁶ This “optimism” expressed the almost religious zeal with which both architect and curator had devoted themselves to the project: for Wright, a temple-tomb of architecture; for Rebay, a “consecrated space” for her collection of non-objective art—“the religion of the future.”²⁷

MAXXI, by contrast, had no collection to display. It was conceived to house the production of a century yet to come. The art that curators and architect envisioned—impermanent and fragile—signaled not optimism, but doubt. Perhaps the labyrinthine complexity of the museum, its drifting paths, and unresolved conclusion stand as a testament to that doubt, as if to declare “an incompleteness, the impossibility of finishing, of totalizing, of saturating”²⁸—words that Jacques Derrida used to characterize another well-known ziggurat, the Tower of Babel.

NOTAS

- ¹ Mark Garcia, "MAXXI, Rome: Zaha Hadid Architects," *AD Architectural Design* 80, n° 3 (2010): 132-135.
- ² Paolo Portoghesi, "Fuori dal coro," *Abitare la terra* 8, n° 25 (2009): 3.
- ³ William Cortes Casarrubios, "Arte contemporanea, supermusei e città in Italia tra anni Ottanta e Duemila," PhD diss. (Università degli studi di Udine, 2023), 215.
- ⁴ Elizabeth M. Merrill, "Zaha Hadid's Center for Contemporary Art and the Perils of New Museum Architecture," *arq: Architectural Research Quarterly* 23, n° 3 (2019): 211.
- ⁵ Concorso di Arte Contemporanea promosso dal Ministero, Programma di concorso, 1998, Pos. 7B: Caserma Montello dal 1997, Folder 2Bis, Archivio della Galleria Nazionale di Arte Moderna (AGNAM), Roma, 8.
- ⁶ "The National center for Contemporary Art and Architecture," MAXXI, May 10, 2017, <https://www.maxxi.art/en/progetto-architettonico/>.
- ⁷ Francesco Garofalo, *Arte futura. Opere e progetti del Centro per le Arti Contemporanee a Roma* (Milano: Electa, 1999), 92–94, 100–102.
- ⁸ Thomas de Monchaux, "A Hard and Lifeless Matter: Notes on Zaha Hadid at the Guggenheim," *Log*, n° 9 (2007): 104.
- ⁹ Nerma Cridge, "Restless: Drawn by Zaha Hadid," in *The Routledge Companion to Women in Architecture*, ed. Anna Sokolina (New York and Abingdon: Routledge, 2021), 296.
- ¹⁰ Centro per le Arti Contemporanee, *Note sul programma per l'area delle caserme di via Guido Reni, Fax di Francesco Garofalo a Sandra*, 1998, Pos. 7B: Caserma Montello dal 1997, Folder 2, Archivio della Galleria Nazionale di Arte Moderna (AGNAM), Roma.
- ¹¹ Concorso di Arte Contemporanea promosso dal Ministero, Programma di concorso, 9.
- ¹² Zaha Hadid, Kenneth Frampton, and Alvin Boyarski, *Planetary Architecture two* (London: Architectural Association, 1983).
- ¹³ Zaha Hadid and Aaron Betsky, *The complete Zaha Hadid* (New York: Rizzoli International, 2009).
- ¹⁴ Zaha Hadid, *Zaha Hadid: 1996–2001* (*El Croquis*, no. 103, 2001), 9–10.
- ¹⁵ Hadid, *Zaha Hadid: 1996–2001*, 31.
- ¹⁶ Portoghesi, "Fuori dal coro," 4.
- ¹⁷ Hans Ulrich Obrist and Zaha Hadid, *Zaha Hadid* (Köln: Walter König, 2007), 46–49; Cortes Casarrubios, "Arte contemporanea, supermusei e città in Italia tra anni Ottanta e Duemila," 231–232, 251.
- ¹⁸ de Monchaux, "A Hard and Lifeless Matter: Notes on Zaha Hadid at the Guggenheim," 104.
- ¹⁹ Lewis Mumford, "What Wright Hath Wrought. Frank Lloyd Wright's radical designs," *The New Yorker* (December 5, 1959): 105–130.
- ²⁰ Beatriz Colomina, "The endless museum: Le Corbusier and Mies van der Rohe," *Log*, n° 15 (2009): 59.
- ²¹ Hadid, *Zaha Hadid: 1996–2001*, 180.
- ²² Desley Luscombe, "Zaha Hadid's notebooks: the sketch in architecture," *The Journal of Architecture* 25, n° 3 (2020): 266–267.
- ²³ Zaha Hadid, *Relazione al progetto definitivo (2001/11 – 2002/06)*, 2001, Fondo 1: Centro per le arti contemporanee, poi MAXXI Museo nazionale delle arti del XXI secolo, Roma, MAXXI Digital Archives.
- ²⁴ Hadid, *Zaha Hadid: 1996–2001*, 181; Hadid, *Relazione al progetto definitivo (2001/11 – 2002/06)*.
- ²⁵ Mumford, "What Wright Hath Wrought. Frank Lloyd Wright's radical designs."
- ²⁶ David Watkin, "Frank Lloyd Wright & the Guggenheim Museum," *AA Files*, n° 21 (1991): 40–48.
- ²⁷ Watkin, "Frank Lloyd Wright & the Guggenheim Museum," 42.
- ²⁸ Mark Wigley, "The translation of architecture, the production of Babel," *Assemblage*, n° 8 (1989): 19.

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